

Clade definitions used for defining the nodes that the ages were extracted from, based on the phylogeny in Figure 1 of the main paper:

(1) Neosuchia (including Thalattosuchia): all crocodyliforms more closely related to *Crocodylus niloticus* than to *Notosuchus terrestris*. (Serenó *et al.* 2001)

(2) Neosuchia (if Thalattosuchia are excluded): Atoposauridae, Goniopholididae, Pholidosauridae, Dyrosauridae, *Bernissartia*, *Shamosuchus* and eusuchians (Benton & Clark 1988)

(3) Dyrosauridae: Phosphatosaurine and Hyposaurinae (Buffetaut 1976; 1980). In our phylogeny: last common ancestor of *Hyposaurus natator oweni* and *Congosaurus compressus* and all its descendants. In Stockdale & Benton (2021): last common ancestor of *Anthracosuchus balrogus* and *Guarinisuchus munizi*.

(4) Goniopholididae: in our phylogeny: last common ancestor of *Vectisuchus leptognathus* and *Goniopholis simus* and all its descendants. In Stockdale & Benton (2021): last common ancestor of *Calsoyasuchus vallcieps* and *Goniopholis simus* and all its descendants

(5) Crocodylia: Last common ancestor of *Gavialis gangeticus*, *Alligator mississippiensis* and *Crocodylus niloticus* and all of its descendants (Gmelin 1789, amended in Brochu 2003). **NOTE: In our phylogeny, the same node also denotes Eusuchia.**

For the Stockdale & Benton (2021) phylogeny, the following definition is applied to Eusuchia: Last common ancestor of *Hylaeochampsa vectiana*, *Crocodylus niloticus*, *Gavialis gangeticus*, and *Alligator mississippiensis* and all of its descendents (Huxley 1975, amended in Brochu 2003). Due to the absence of *Hylaeochampsa vectiana* in the phylogeny, *Iharkutosuchus makadii* is used instead.

(6) Hylaeochampsidae: A node-based clade stemming from the most recent common ancestor of *Hylaeochampsa vectiana*, *Iharkutosuchus makadii*, *Pachycheilosuchus trinquei* and *Pietraroiasuchus ormezzanoi* (Buscalioni *et al.* 2011). Simplified definition for our G21 phylogeny: last common ancestor of *Hylaeochampsa vectiana* and *Pietraroiasuchus formidabilis* and all its descendants.

(7) Gavialoidea: *Gavialis gangeticus* and all crocodylians closer to it than to *Alligator mississippiensis* or *Crocodylus niloticus* (Case 1930)

(8) Gavialinae: In our phylogeny: last common ancestor of *Eogavialis africanum* and *Gavialis gangeticus* and all its descendants.

(9) Tomistominae: *Tomistoma schlegelii* and all crocodylians closer to it than to *Crocodylus niloticus* (Kälin 1955)

(10) Brevirostres: last common ancestor of *Alligator mississippiensis* and *Crocodylus niloticus* and all of its descendants (von Zittel 1890). Note: In the Stockdale & Benton (2021) phylogeny, this would also include Gavialoidea and is thus excluded.

(11) Crocodyloidea: *Crocodylus niloticus* and all crocodylians closer to it than to *Alligator mississippiensis* or *Gavialis gangeticus* (Fitzinger 1826). Note: for Stockdale & Benton (2021), this means that Crocodyloidea is the same as Crocodylidae, due to the position of Gavialinae.

(12) Crocodylidae: last common ancestor of *Crocodylus niloticus*, *Osteolaemus tetraspis*, and *Tomistoma schlegelii* and all of its descendants (Cuvier 1807). For Stockdale & Benton (2021): the last common ancestor of *Crocodylus niloticus*, *Osteolaemus tetraspis* and *Kambara implexidens*, and all of its descendants (thus including Crocodylinae + Mekosuchinae).

(13) Crocodylinae: *Crocodylus niloticus* and all crocodylians closer to it than to *Tomistoma schlegelii* (Cuvier 1807). For Stockdale & Benton (2021): *Crocodylus niloticus* and all crocodylians closer to it than to Mekosuchinae.

(14) Alligatoroidea: *Alligator mississippiensis* and all crocodylians closer to it than to *Crocodylus niloticus* or *Gavialis gangeticus* (Gray 1844)

(15) Diplocynodontinae: *Diplocynodon ungeri* and all crocodylians closer to it than to *Alligator mississippiensis* or *Crocodylus niloticus* (amended based on Brochu 1999, as our phylogeny does not include *Diplocynodon ratelii*)

(16) Globidonta: last common ancestor of *Navajosuchus novomexicanus* and *Melanosuchus niger* and all its descendants. **NOTE: modified definition according to our phylogeny – original definition by Brochu 1999 is not applicable due to the different position of Diplocynodontinae.** For Stockdale & Benton (2021), the definition of Brochu (1999) applies: *Alligator mississippiensis* and all crocodylians closer to it than to *Diplocynodon ratelii*.

(17) Caimaninae: *Caiman crocodilus* and all crocodylians closer to it than to *Alligator sinensis* (amended from Norell 1988 in Brochu 2003)

For Stockdale & Benton (2021) only:

(18) Tethysuchia: *Pholidosaurus purbeckensis*, *Dyrosaurus phosphaticus*, their common ancestor and all its descendants (de Andrade *et al.* 2011). As *Pholidosaurus purbeckensis* is absent in this phylogeny, *Khoratosuchus jintasakuli* is used instead.

(19) Mekosuchinae: last common ancestor of *Kambara murgonensis*, *Australosuchus clarkae*, *Pallimnarchus pollens*, *Baru darrowi*, *Trilophosuchus rackhami*, *Quinkana fortirostrum*, and *Mekosuchus inexpectatus* and all of its descendants (Balouet & Buffetaut 1987, adapted from Salisbury & Willis 1996 in Brochu 2003)

(20) Alligatoridae: Last common ancestor of *Alligator mississippiensis* and *Caiman crocodilus* and all of its descendants (Cuvier 1807)

(21) Alligatorinae: *Alligator mississippiensis* and all crocodylians closer to it than to *Caiman crocodilus* (Kälin 1940)

(22) Thalattosuchia: Metryiorhynchidae + Teleosauridae (Fraas 1901 and Buffetaut 1982)